

Optimization of High Endurance Single Wing UAV

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Abstract

Efforts to create worldwide internet accessibility are familiar pursuits to large scale companies such as Facebook with their Aquila project. This research seeks to optimize the endurance of a single wing high-altitude UAV design considering mostly aerodynamics and battery design. Design variables based off of span, chord, velocity, sweep angle, washout, battery size, angle of attack, etc., will expand current research exploring the optimal aerodynamics of UAVs with optimized lithium batteries. Results were obtained using non-gradient and gradient-based optimization methods.

Introduction

One of Facebook's latest endeavors involves connecting the world to the internet through the initiative called Internet.org. As part of this effort, Facebook's R&D department has been engineering a drone (dubbed Aquila) capable of beaming high speed Internet access to areas of the world that lack Internet access.

Previous research has already demonstrated the usefulness and robustness of UAVs and their ability to remain in the air for months or even years at a time[1][2][3][4]. The Aquila drone plans to incorporate previous work by travelling at altitudes ranging between 60,000 and 90,000 ft, utilizing solar power, and staying in the air for at least 3 months at a time. Meeting these requirements is a significant engineering task that will require the drone be optimized for its intended function.

Optimization algorithms for varying UAVs are common in current literature. Many focus

on optimizing specific aspects in regards to flight endurance, such as motor and propeller optimization, rather than the full set of variables that will maximize the overall vehicle.

Existing efforts to optimize UAV endurance have done so through differing methodologies. Batill et al. focused on the areas of aerodynamics, weights, propulsion, flight performance, and stability/control in optimizing the design of electric powered UAVs [5]. Abbe et al. and Zhu et al. both outlined multiple concerns that need to be taken into account when designing solar powered aircraft[6]. Zhu points out that achieving an energy balance during daytime and nighttime flying states is a critical part of long endurance solar aircraft design. Others have also optimized motor and propeller incorporation in UAVs[7], modeled practical solar energy implementations[8], and considered high altitude, high endurance modeling[9]. This research combines techniques into an overarching optimization problem, and hopes to expand on previous research in multiple ways.

This paper will explore using non-gradient based optimization techniques, to maximize the endurance of the specified UAV. Primary design variables include span, chord, velocity, washout angle, and airfoil shape, and angle of attack. At a future time, additional design variables may be incorporated such as taper ratio, battery type, motor type and others. Although some of the previous factors were considered in this optimization, they were used solely as user configurable parameters rather than design variables.

Methodology

Objective Function

One of the critical factors that determines the endurance of a UAV is its power consumption. When the stored energy level in the UAV reaches a critically low level, the UAV must return to the ground to be recharged. The net power output of a UAV determines how fast that energy is depleted. Considering the energy balance of a UAV's batteries, the drone's power supply is depleted when the following condition is true:

$$E_{st,0} + (\dot{E}_{in} - \dot{E}_{out})t = E_{lo} \quad (1)$$

Here, $E_{st,0}$ denotes the initial battery energy level, \dot{E}_{in} denotes the power coming into the UAV, \dot{E}_{out} denotes the power being expended by the UAV, t is time, and E_{lo} is a fixed critically low energy level at which the UAV must return to be recharged. The time that the UAV can last in the air can then be expressed as follows:

$$t = \frac{E_{st,0} - E_{lo}}{(\dot{E}_{out} - \dot{E}_{in})} \quad (2)$$

Maximizing this endurance time is the primary goal for Facebook and other solar powered drone developers. However, when inverted this function can be expressed as a minimization problem:

$$\frac{1}{t} = \frac{(\dot{E}_{out} - \dot{E}_{in})}{E_{st,0} - E_{lo}} \quad (3)$$

It is clear that if endurance is to be maximized, the net power output $\dot{E}_{out} - \dot{E}_{in}$ must be minimized. Although maximizing $E_{st,0} - E_{lo}$ will also help maximize endurance, we will focus on minimizing the net power in this analysis.

The components of output power include thrust and communication instrumentation. Thrust is the main component of output power in the UAV being considered. The power expended through thrust is equal to $T * V$. Since much of the UAV's mission will consist of loitering in a circle with a 2 mile radius, we approximate its main flight pattern as a constant altitude, constant velocity trajectory. In this

state, the thrust would need to equal the UAV's drag:

$$T * V = D * V = \frac{1}{2}V^3\rho(S)C_D \quad (4)$$

The coefficient of drag C_D can be expressed in different ways depending on the choice of book-keeping. For our model, we used the following expression:

$$C_D = C_{Dp} + C_{Di} \quad (5)$$

Here, C_{Dp} refers to the parasitic drag, which is a function of form factor k , skin friction coefficient c_f , and wetted surface area S_{wet} . C_{Di} is the induced drag which is a function of the coefficient of lift C_L , the wing aspect ratio AR , and the Oswald efficiency factor e . Rewriting equation (5):

$$C_D = kc_fS_{wet} + \frac{C_L^2}{\pi AR e} \quad (6)$$

The second component of the UAV's power expenditure is its communication instrumentation. Because of a lack of information on the specific instruments that will be used, we reserved this part for future analyses when more information will hopefully be available.

The only components that will replenish the UAV's batteries with power are its solar panels. We used data corresponding to thin film GaAs solar panels due to their flexibility, relatively low weight, and relatively high efficiency for single junction cells. Multijunction cells have higher solar efficiencies, but were ultimately not chosen because of their high cost. The power obtained through the solar panels is expressed as

$$I * S * \eta \quad (7)$$

where I is the amount of solar irradiation, S is the planform area of the wing, and η is the solar cell efficiency. For our optimization, we based the irradiation off of a location on the border of Nepal and India where Facebook's UAVs could be deployed in the future. We set the solar cell efficiency equal to 27.5%, based upon a single-junction GaAs solar panel developed by LG Electronics.

Combining the output and input powers into the net output power equation, we get the following result:

$$\dot{E}_{out} - \dot{E}_{in} = \frac{1}{2} \rho S V^3 (k c_f S_{wet} + \frac{C_L^2}{\pi A R e}) - I * S * \eta \quad (8)$$

Battery

Previous articles suggest that a UAV's electric propulsion system can take up to 60% of the UAV weight[10]. Thus we felt that significant weight reductions could be seen by optimizing this component. The battery portion of the drone must be optimized to store enough energy to run for approximately 16 hours without solar energy, have the smallest amount of possible weight, and use the most efficient space to maintain the battery's operating temperature while minimizing the amount of heat loss. Using E_{stored} as the energy capacity of the battery, E_{loss} as the heat loss from the battery over 16 hours, and $weight$ as the combined weight of the battery and insulation the objective function we minimized is:

$$Obj = \frac{-(E_{stored} - E_{loss})}{weight} \quad (9)$$

The design variables used in this optimization include the dimensions of the battery (x - measured along the chord, y - measured along the wingspan, and z - measured along the wing thickness), the thickness of the insulation, and the placement of the battery along the wing. Parameters include the wing properties (chord, wingspan, thickness, thermal coefficient, and skin thickness), velocity of the drone, required energy storage to run the drone, stored energy safety factors (as percentages; eg. 1.1 = 110%), the face of the battery that attaches to the spar, battery properties (specific energy, energy density, and minimum operating temperature), insulation properties (thermal coefficient, density, and minimum manufacturable thickness), air properties at the desired test altitude (thermal coefficient, density, ambient temperature, Prandtl number, dynamic viscosity), spar properties (thermal coefficient, thickness, and avail-

able space inside the spar for the battery [X, Y, Z]), and optimization tolerance.

For our optimization run, we assumed a closed cell polyurethane foam for the insulation. The estimated material properties are:

$$k = 0.02 \frac{W}{m * K}, \rho = 8.01 \frac{kg}{m^3}, t_{min} = 10^{-3} m \quad (10)$$

As mentioned in the paragraph above, the optimization can be run with any kind of insulation by altering the input properties.

The energy loss from the battery is modeled as six 1-d conductive heat losses. This heat loss assumes the battery is maintained at a uniform temperature and takes into account the entrapped air inside the spar, the insulation itself, spar and wing materials, and the convective component due to the velocity of the drone and the outside properties of the air. Because the face of the battery that is attached to the spar will not have an air buffer of insulation, the heat loss through that face must be calculated specifically for that case. With the exception of the inner face (at the center of the drone), it has been assumed that the other faces are symmetric in their heat losses.

Constraints

To maintain feasibility, we subjected our design to several constraints. First, no point on an aircraft's wing loading can exceed C_{Lmax} at any time. This constraint prevents against any stall conditions developing on the wing.

Second, the stress at any point in a wing must not exceed the yield stress of the wing spar material. Since specific information on the wing material for Facebook's drone is not available, we modeled the wing spars as being made of plain-weave carbon fiber. We modeled the shape of each spar as a simple hollow rectangular prism with a wall thickness of 5 mm, a height equal to that of the airfoil maximum thickness, and a width equal to one third of the root chord.

Third, the overall lift of an aircraft must be at least as great as the aircraft's weight. Current reports put the weight of Facebook's Aquila drone at about 880 lbs, which we used as the baseline for the weight of our UAV.

Fourth, to guard against stall the velocity of an aircraft should remain greater than about 1.2 times the stall velocity, where

$$V_{stall} = \sqrt{\frac{W}{\frac{1}{2}\rho SC_L}} \quad (11)$$

Fifth, to achieve a balanced flight state, the moment coefficient of an aircraft must be as close to zero as possible. We constrained the moment coefficient to be between -.02 and .02, and are anticipating that control surfaces will bring the moment coefficient completely to zero.

Design Variables

Considering the objective and constraints mentioned above, we chose to minimize the objective with respect to the following design variables:

- b The UAV wing span
- AoA The angle of attack of the wing
- \bar{c} The UAV mean chord
- ψ The leading edge sweep angle
- θ Washout angle

These variables affect both the magnitude of the drag put on the airplane and the wing planform area upon which solar panels can be mounted. Although not a variable, it should be mentioned that the MH60 airfoil was used as the airfoil for the UAV.

Separately, the battery optimization uses many of the previous design variables as parameters and/or constraints and instead uses the following design variables:

- x Battery x-dimension
- y Battery y-dimension
- z Battery z-dimension
- t_i Battery Insulation Thickness

Results

Optimization

The Athena Vortex Lattice program (AVL), by Dr. Mark Drela from MIT and Harold Youngren, was used to compute the values of C_L and e . The Python programming language was used as the framework for solving the optimization problem. The SNOPT commercial optimizer was used as the actual optimization algorithm. Multiple optimizations have already been run on the main objective function. Because they were run before the objective function has been fully refined however, most of the results will not be included in the extended outline.

The tests were run with the assumption that the UAV was going at an airspeed of 25 m/s. A density of .11025 kg per cubic meter was used—a value based upon tabulated data for air density at the target height for Aquila.

NSGA2 Method

Figure 1: Result for NSGA2

Using the NSGA2 method of non-gradient optimization the following results were obtained for wing optimization.

Initial b	40 m
Initial AoA	5 Deg
Initial c	30.49 m
Initial ψ	25 Deg
Initial θ	-3 Deg

Table 1: NSGA Starting Values

Final b	45.605 m
Final AoA	9.271 Deg
Final c	3.930 m
Final ψ	0.643 Deg
Final θ	-3.59 Deg
Final Energy Consumption	6536.918 W

Table 2: NSGA Final Values

Battery x dimensions	0.327 m
Battery y dimensions	2.052 m
Battery z dimensions	0.267 m
Battery Weight	164.42 kg
Total Energy Stored	2.07e8 J
Heat Loss	1.323 W

Table 3: 1st Case Battery Optimization

ALPSO Method

The starting values for the ALPSO method were retrieved from previous test data endpoints after performing an initial ALPSO test on generalized values. Due to several unknown, after 100 function calls the result was obtained.

Initial b	49.58 m
Initial c	2.24 m
Initial AoA	10.0 Deg
Initial ψ	2.26 Deg
Initial θ	0.0 Deg

Table 4: ALPSO Initial Values

Figure 2: Result for ALPSO

Final b	33.364 m
Final c	1.891 m
Final AoA	5.076 Deg
Final ψ	10.580 Deg
Final θ	-0.142 Deg
Final Energy Consumption	1869.729 W

Table 5: ALPSO Final Values

Battery x dimensions	0.180 m
Battery y dimensions	2.052 m
Battery z dimensions	0.138 m
Battery Weight	46.544 kg
Total Energy Stored	5.86e7 J
Heat Loss	0.645 W

Table 6: 2nd Case Battery Optimization

Both lithium-ion and lithium-sulfur batteries were tested. It was found that the higher specific energy of lithium-sulfur resulted in a lower overall weight and thus a better optimum. The properties of the lithium-sulfur batteries were obtained from <http://www.sionpower.com/pdf/articles/LIS%20Spec%20Sheet%2010-3-08.pdf>

Discussion

The results we obtained from the NSGA2 method tended towards having a high angle of attack, a high chord, and a low sweep angle. The high angle of attack is most likely because of the

relatively low velocity (25 m/s) and low density of air at the target altitude. Because of this, the angle of attack had to increase to the limit to help the aircraft generate enough lift to overcome the weight of its components and payload.

The high chord was most likely due to our limited model for parasitic drag. Large chords drastically increase the drag, but the optimizer maximized the chord anyways since AVL was not able to model accurately the increased drag associated with a large chord. In addition, the solar model in the objective rewarded the design for having a larger surface area, since a larger surface area meant more energy from the solar panels.

Finally, the low sweep angle can be explained by the nature of the MH60 airfoil. This particular airfoil was designed by Dr. Martin Hepperle specifically for tailless aircraft. It was designed to have a very low moment coefficient in order to minimize the need for an empannage. It should be noted that several successful NASA solar-powered aircraft have had minimal sweep angles such as the Pathfinder and Helios Prototype.

Trial runs of the battery optimization code demonstrated that the insulation tended toward the minimum manufacturable thickness. Because of this, the code was modified to run a second optimization run with no insulation at all and compare the results to the optimization with insulation. The outcome was that the battery with no insulation consistently performs better. This shows that it is better to use the available weight and space solely for the battery than to include insulation as a means of minimizing heat loss. While this was tested only with polyurethane foam, it is expected to be the same for any insulation material under the necessary requirements for maximum endurance of UAVs.

Conclusions

Expansion Areas

The subject of aircraft optimization is simultaneously broad and deep. Many possible areas of further investigation could be added to our anal-

ysis in order to maximize the endurance of Facebook's Aquila drone. A comprehensive review of these areas is beyond the scope of this paper, but we will touch on a few that might be most impactful in future investigations.

Solar Energy Model. The solar energy model used in this analysis is extremely basic and does not take into account any variations of irradiation exposure due to wing dihedral or aircraft orientation during maneuvers. These considerations could be included in future analyses.

Structural Model. The structural model used in this paper serves only as a ballpark estimate for preventing structural failure. Finite element analysis and other high fidelity tools could be used in future work to analyze the details of structural integrity and vibrational modes. Future optimization work could focus on the optimal structure to be used within the UAV body, as it was assumed in this paper that the only structure present was a main spar spanning the length of the wing.

Material Model. There remains great potential for the material selection of the UAV to be optimized in order to maximize performance and minimize weight. Average properties for a simple plain-weave carbon fiber reinforced composite material were used for the yield stress in this analysis. The selection and combination of fiber and matrix components could be greatly improved to find a higher performing material. The layup schedule of the composite could also be optimized to produce a higher strength to weight ratio.

In-depth Aerodynamic Analysis. The results found by the Athena Vortex Lattice program in this analysis are by no means comprehensive. Further analysis could be conducted with higher fidelity CFD programs to more completely model the performance of the UAV in multiple configurations. CFD analysis would also allow for the optimization of winglets and other aerodynamic features that AVL does not have the ability to model.

Instrument Power Consumption. No information was available to the authors about the instrumentation specifications at the time of writing this article. If this information was made avail-

able, the instrument power requirements could be included in the objective function.

Variable Atmospheric properties. Facebook's current plan is for the UAVs to fly between 60,000 and 90,000 feet. Optimization involving atmospheric properties at the UAV's specific location could help determine the altitude at which minimum power could be consumed, while taking into account the safe flying height at which the UAV would be above any major weather disturbances. Furthermore, atmospheric data could be used to find a better estimate of the level of irradiation the UAV would receive depending on the local atmospheric properties.

Rise and glide engine use. The current optimization assumes that the drone propellers will be continuously running. However, alternate methods of maintaining elevation exist including engine use used to generate a rise in elevation followed by a shut-down of the engines and allowing the drone to glide for a time. These alternate methods could be used to find the most optimal engine (and thus energy) use for the drone.

Higher fidelity heat transfer model. 1-D conduction is a simple and widely used assumption for heat transfer, however a higher fidelity model will more accurately represent the heat transfer conditions the UAV experiences. This higher fidelity model would consider 2-D conduction and irradiation effects (which are likely to be quite significant at higher altitudes).

References

- [1] Sean Montgomery and Nikos Mourtos. *Design of a 5 Kilogram Solar-Powered Unmanned Airplane for Perpetual Solar Endurance Flight*, 49th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference, Joint Propulsion Conferences, (AIAA 2013-3875).
- [2] R. Austin. *Unmanned Aircraft Systems, UAVS Design, Development and Deployment* Wiley, Chichester, West Sussex, United Kingdom (2010)
- [3] Spyridon G. Kontogiannis, John A. Ekaeterinaris, *Design, performance evaluation and optimization of a UAV*, Aerospace Science and Technology, Volume 29, Issue 1, August 2013, Pages 339-350, ISSN 1270-9638.
- [4] A. Noth, *Design of solar powered airplanes for continuous flight*, (Ph.D. thesis) ETH ZRICH (2008) http://www.sky-sailor.ethz.ch/docs/Conceptual_Design_of_Solar_Powered_Airplanes_for_continuous_flight.pdf
- [5] Stephen M. Batill, Marc A. Stelmack, Xiong Qing Yu, *Multidisciplinary design optimization of an electric-powered unmanned air vehicle*, Aircraft Design, Volume 2, Issue 1, March 1999, Pages 1-18, ISSN 1369-8869
- [6] Xiongfeng Zhu, Zheng Guo, Zhongxi Hou, *Solar-powered airplanes: A historical perspective and future challenges*, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Volume 71, November 2014, Pages 36-53, ISSN 0376-0421.
- [7] E. R. Retana and H. Rodriguez-Cortes, *Basic Small Fixed Wing Aircraft Sizing Optimizing Endurance*, Electrical and Electronics Engineering, 2007. ICEEE 2007. 4th International Conference on, Mexico City, 2007, pp. 322-325.
- [8] Xian-Zhong Gao, Zhong-Xi Hou, Zheng Guo, Jian-Xia Liu, Xiao-Qian Chen, *Energy management strategy for solar-powered high-altitude long-endurance aircraft*, Energy Conversion and Management, Volume 70, June 2013, Pages 20-30, ISSN 0196-8904.
- [9] Enrico Cestino, *Design of solar high altitude long endurance aircraft for multi payload & operations*, Aerospace Science and Technology, Volume 10, Issue 6, September 2006, Pages 541-550, ISSN 1270-9638.

- [10] Ohad, Gur., and Aviv, Rosen., *Optimizing Electric Propulsion Systems for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles*, JOURNAL OF AIRCRAFT , Vol.46, No. 4, August 2009